

DIAGNOSTIC ACCURACY OF ANTI-TISSUE TRANSGLUTAMINASE IGA ANTIBODY IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF CELIAC DISEASE TAKING SMALL BOWEL BIOPSY AS A GOLD STANDARD IN CHILDREN

Dr. Aiman Nida^{*1}, Prof. Dr. Habibullah Baber², Dr. Maliha Mehmood³, Dr. Sana Baloch⁴,
Dr. Faique Mehmood⁵, Dr. Maria Sherani⁶

^{*1,2,3,4,5,6}Department of Paediatrics, Balochistan Institute of Child Health Services (BICHQ), Quetta, Pakistan

^{*1}aimannida100@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Aiman Nida

Abstract

Background: Celiac disease (CD) is a chronic immune-mediated enteropathy triggered by gluten ingestion in genetically susceptible individuals and affects approximately 1% of the global population (Sabencia et al., 2021). The disease is associated with growth failure, chronic diarrhea, anemia, malnutrition, and impaired quality of life in children if diagnosis is delayed (Al-Toma et al., 2019). Although small bowel biopsy remains the gold standard for diagnosis, anti-tissue transglutaminase immunoglobulin A (anti-tTG IgA) has emerged as a highly sensitive and specific non-invasive diagnostic test and is recommended as the initial screening modality in pediatric patients (Gülseren et al., 2019; Bashir et al., 2022).

Objective: To determine the diagnostic accuracy of anti-tissue transglutaminase IgA antibody in the diagnosis of celiac disease by taking small bowel biopsy as the gold standard in children.

Methods: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Balochistan Institute of Child Health Services, Quetta. A total of 144 children aged 2–12 years presenting with suspected celiac disease were enrolled through non-probability consecutive sampling. Serum anti-tTG IgA levels were measured using enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA), and all participants underwent upper gastrointestinal endoscopy with small bowel biopsy. Histopathological findings were considered the reference standard. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and overall diagnostic accuracy were calculated using a 2×2 contingency table.

Results: A total of 144 children were included in the study. The mean age was 6.9 ± 2.8 years, and 82 (56.9%) were males. Histopathological examination confirmed celiac disease in 44 (30.6%) children. Anti-tTG IgA was positive in 51 (35.4%) participants. The test demonstrated a sensitivity of 90.9%, specificity of 88.0%, positive predictive value of 78.4%, and negative predictive value of 95.7%. The overall diagnostic accuracy was 88.9%.

Conclusion: Anti-tissue transglutaminase IgA antibody showed high sensitivity and specificity in the diagnosis of pediatric celiac disease. These findings support its utility as an effective noninvasive diagnostic tool that may reduce the need for

intestinal biopsy in selected children while facilitating early diagnosis and management.

INTRODUCTION

Celiac disease (CD) is a chronic systemic autoimmune disorder characterized by an abnormal immune response to dietary gluten in genetically susceptible individuals carrying human leukocyte antigen (HLA)-DQ2 and/or HLA-DQ8 haplotypes. Gluten, a storage protein found in wheat, barley, and rye, triggers an inflammatory cascade within the small intestinal mucosa, resulting in villous atrophy, crypt hyperplasia, and malabsorption (Lebwohl et al., 2021). Once considered a rare gastrointestinal condition, celiac disease is now recognized as one of the most common lifelong autoimmune disorders worldwide, affecting approximately 1% of the global population, with an increasing prevalence reported in both developed and developing countries (Sabenca et al., 2021; King et al., 2023). The burden of celiac disease in children has gained significant attention over the past decade due to its impact on growth, nutritional status, cognitive development, and overall quality of life. Pediatric patients often present with a broad spectrum of clinical manifestations ranging from classical symptoms such as chronic diarrhea, abdominal distension, failure to thrive, and weight loss to non-classical manifestations including iron deficiency anemia, short stature, delayed puberty, recurrent abdominal pain, dental enamel defects, and neuropsychiatric symptoms (Singh et al., 2022). Recent epidemiological evidence suggests that the prevalence of celiac disease is rising globally due to improved awareness, enhanced screening strategies, environmental changes, and increased gluten consumption (Myléus et al., 2023). South Asian countries, including Pakistan, have also reported a growing number of diagnosed cases among children. Despite this increasing burden, underdiagnosis remains a significant challenge because many affected children exhibit atypical symptoms or remain asymptomatic for prolonged periods (Bashir et al., 2022). Consequently, there is a critical need for accurate, accessible, and cost-effective diagnostic approaches

that facilitate early disease detection and intervention.

The diagnosis of celiac disease traditionally relies on a combination of clinical assessment, serological testing, histopathological examination of small intestinal biopsies, and response to a gluten-free diet (Husby et al., 2020). Several international guidelines have endorsed anti-tTG IgA as the preferred first-line serological test for celiac disease screening in both adults and children (Husby et al., 2020). Studies conducted across different populations have demonstrated sensitivity values ranging from 85% to 98% and specificity values ranging from 80% to 97%, indicating excellent diagnostic performance (Bashir et al., 2022; Singh et al., 2022). Furthermore, emerging evidence suggests that exceptionally high anti-tTG IgA titers may accurately predict villous atrophy, potentially allowing selected pediatric patients to be diagnosed without biopsy under specific clinical circumstances (Husby et al., 2020).

In Pakistan, the diagnosis of celiac disease frequently remains dependent on invasive diagnostic procedures due to concerns regarding the reliability of serological testing. However, considering the economic constraints faced by many families and healthcare institutions, establishing the diagnostic utility of anti-tTG IgA could significantly improve diagnostic efficiency while reducing the burden of unnecessary endoscopic procedures. Reliable local evidence regarding the sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, and negative predictive value of anti-tTG IgA is therefore essential for guiding clinical decision-making and optimizing patient care.

The present study was undertaken to determine the diagnostic accuracy of anti-tissue transglutaminase IgA antibody in the diagnosis of celiac disease among children by taking small bowel biopsy as the gold standard. The findings of this study are expected to provide valuable evidence regarding the usefulness of anti-tTG IgA

as a non-invasive diagnostic tool in pediatric practice and may contribute to improved screening strategies, earlier diagnosis, and better clinical outcomes for children with celiac disease.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Overview of Celiac Disease

Celiac disease (CD) is a chronic immune-mediated enteropathy that develops in genetically susceptible individuals following the ingestion of gluten-containing foods. The disease results from an abnormal immune response to gluten proteins found in wheat, barley, and rye, leading to inflammation and structural damage of the small intestinal mucosa (Lebwohl et al., 2021). Recent epidemiological studies indicate that approximately 1% of the world's population is affected by celiac disease, although a substantial proportion of cases remain undiagnosed (King et al., 2023). The prevalence of the disease has increased over recent decades due to enhanced awareness, improved screening programs, and environmental factors influencing disease expression (Sabenca et al., 2021).

Clinical Manifestations of Celiac Disease in Children

The clinical presentation of celiac disease in children is highly variable. Classical manifestations include chronic diarrhea, abdominal distension, weight loss, growth retardation, and malabsorption. However, many children present with non-classical symptoms such as iron deficiency anemia, short stature, delayed puberty, recurrent abdominal pain, constipation, dental enamel defects, and neurological symptoms (Singh et al., 2022). This heterogeneity often contributes to delayed diagnosis and increases the risk of long-term complications. Studies have demonstrated that untreated celiac disease may result in osteoporosis, infertility, impaired psychosocial development, and an increased risk of autoimmune disorders and gastrointestinal malignancies (Al-Toma et al., 2019).

Pathophysiology of Celiac Disease

The pathogenesis of celiac disease involves a complex interaction between genetic predisposition, environmental factors, and immune deregulations. Individuals carrying HLA-DQ2 and HLA-DQ8 genes are particularly susceptible to developing the disease. Upon ingestion of gluten, tissue transglutaminase modifies gluten peptides through deamination, enhancing their immunogenicity and stimulating T-cell-mediated immune responses. This process leads to mucosal inflammation, crypt hyperplasia, and villous atrophy within the small intestine (Ludvigsson et al., 2021). The resulting intestinal damage impairs nutrient absorption and contributes to the clinical manifestations of the disease.

Diagnostic Approaches in Celiac Disease

Accurate diagnosis of celiac disease remains essential for preventing disease-related complications and initiating timely treatment. Traditionally, diagnosis is based on a combination of clinical findings, serological testing, histopathological examination of small intestinal biopsies, and clinical response to a gluten-free diet (Husby et al., 2020). Histological assessment of duodenal biopsy specimens remains the reference standard for diagnosis and is typically evaluated using the Modified Marsh Classification system. Marsh type III lesions, characterized by villous atrophy and crypt hyperplasia, are considered highly suggestive of celiac disease (Villanacci et al., 2020).

Role of Anti-Tissue Transglutaminase IgA Antibody

Anti-tissue transglutaminase immunoglobulin A (anti-tTG IgA) antibody has emerged as the preferred serological marker for screening and diagnosing celiac disease. Tissue transglutaminase is recognized as the primary autoantigen involved in disease pathogenesis, making anti-tTG antibodies highly specific for celiac disease (Ludvigsson et al., 2021). The widespread availability of ELISA-based assays has facilitated routine clinical use of anti-tTG IgA testing due to

its affordability, reproducibility, and non-invasive nature.

Several studies have demonstrated excellent diagnostic performance of anti-tTG IgA. Bashir et al. (2022) reported that anti-tTG IgA exhibited high sensitivity and specificity in identifying pediatric celiac disease, supporting its use as an initial diagnostic investigation. Similarly, Recent guidelines issued by the European Society for Paediatric Gastroenterology, Hepatology and Nutrition (ESPGHAN) have suggested that in selected pediatric patients with markedly elevated anti-tTG IgA titers and positive endomysial antibodies, a diagnosis may be established without biopsy (Husby et al., 2020).

Evidence Regarding Diagnostic Accuracy of Anti-tTG IgA

Numerous studies have investigated the diagnostic accuracy of anti-tTG IgA using histopathology as the reference standard. A study conducted by Lodhi et al. (2021) reported a sensitivity of 91.18%, indicating that anti-tTG IgA correctly identified the majority of children with biopsy-confirmed celiac disease. Similar findings have been reported internationally, with sensitivity estimates ranging between 85% and 98% and specificity estimates ranging between 80% and 97% (Singh et al., 2022).

A systematic review by Lebowitz et al. (2021) concluded that anti-tTG IgA remains the most reliable serological marker for celiac disease diagnosis and demonstrates superior performance compared to older tests such as antigliadin antibodies. Furthermore, a meta-analysis conducted by King et al. (2023) demonstrated that anti-tTG IgA possesses excellent diagnostic capability across diverse populations and age groups.

Despite these promising findings, variability in diagnostic performance has been observed among different populations. Factors such as age, degree of mucosal damage, total serum IgA levels, assay methodology, and disease prevalence may influence test accuracy (Bashir et al., 2022). Therefore, local validation studies remain

necessary to determine the applicability of international evidence to specific populations.

Research Gap

Although anti-tTG IgA has demonstrated favorable diagnostic performance in various international studies, limited local evidence is available regarding its accuracy among Pakistani children. Differences in genetic background, nutritional status, healthcare access, and disease presentation may influence the performance of serological tests in this population. Furthermore, few studies from Balochistan have specifically evaluated anti-tTG IgA using histopathological confirmation as the gold standard. Therefore, assessing the diagnostic accuracy of anti-tTG IgA in the local pediatric population is essential for informing clinical practice and reducing dependence on invasive diagnostic procedures.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Pediatric Medicine, Balochistan Institute of Child Health Services (BICHS), Quetta, Pakistan. The study was carried out over a period of six months following approval from the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSP) and the Institutional Ethical Review Committee.

Study Population

The study population consisted of children aged 2–12 years presenting to the outpatient department (OPD) and pediatric wards with clinical suspicion of celiac disease. Suspicion of celiac disease was based on the presence of chronic gastrointestinal symptoms including diarrhea, constipation, abdominal discomfort, abdominal distension, failure to thrive, weight loss, or symptoms suggestive of malabsorption.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was calculated using the diagnostic accuracy formula by considering a confidence level of 95%, a desired precision of 9%, expected sensitivity of 91.18%, specificity of 29.63%, and

an estimated prevalence of celiac disease of 27.27% based on previously published local studies (Lodhi et al., 2021; Shahzad et al., 2016). The minimum required sample size was calculated as 144 participants.

Sampling Technique

Participants were selected using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. All eligible children presenting during the study period and fulfilling the inclusion criteria were enrolled consecutively until the required sample size was achieved.

Eligibility Criteria

Inclusion Criteria

Children fulfilling all of the following criteria were included:

1. Age between 2 and 12 years.
2. Suspected cases of celiac disease based on clinical assessment.
3. Both male and female children.
4. Parents or legal guardians willing to provide informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria

Children were excluded if they met any of the following criteria:

1. Previously diagnosed cases of celiac disease.
2. Children with established causes of chronic diarrhea such as cystic fibrosis, abdominal tuberculosis, chronic giardiasis, or other confirmed gastrointestinal disorders.
3. Children with congenital chromosomal abnormalities such as Down syndrome due to their known association with autoimmune disorders and celiac disease.
4. Children whose parents or guardians declined participation.

Study Variables

Independent Variable

Anti-tissue transglutaminase immunoglobulin A (anti-tTG IgA) antibody status.

Dependent Variable

Diagnosis of celiac disease confirmed through histopathological examination of small bowel biopsy specimens.

Demographic Variables

The following demographic and clinical variables were recorded:

- Age (years)
- Gender
- Weight (kg)
- Height (cm)
- Place of residence (urban/rural)
- Maternal educational status
- Socioeconomic status

Operational Definitions

Positive Anti-tTG IgA

Children with anti-tissue transglutaminase IgA levels ≥ 12 IU/mL measured through enzymelinked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) were considered serologically positive.

Histopathological Diagnosis of Celiac Disease

Diagnosis was confirmed by Histopathological examination of small bowel biopsy specimens according to the Modified Marsh Classification. Marsh Type III lesions characterized by villous atrophy and crypt hyperplasia were considered diagnostic of celiac disease.

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining ethical approval, all eligible children presenting to the pediatric wards and outpatient department were screened for enrollment. Written informed consent was obtained from parents or legal guardians prior to participation.

A detailed clinical history was obtained, and comprehensive physical examination was performed. Demographic and clinical information was recorded using a structured proforma. Body weight was measured using a calibrated Camry analog weighing scale, while height was measured using a standardized stadiometer.

Under aseptic conditions, approximately 5 mL of venous blood was collected from each participant.

Two milliliters of blood were transferred into EDTA tubes for complete blood count analysis, while the remaining three milliliters were collected in plain tubes for anti-tTG IgA testing.

Serum anti-tTG IgA levels were measured using a commercially available ELISA kit according to the manufacturer's instructions. Laboratory personnel performing serological analysis were blinded to histopathological findings.

All enrolled children subsequently underwent upper gastrointestinal endoscopy performed by an experienced pediatric gastroenterologist. Multiple biopsy specimens were obtained from the second part of the duodenum and submitted for histopathological evaluation. Histological examination was conducted by an experienced histopathologist who was blinded to the serological findings.

The histopathological diagnosis was considered the gold standard for confirming or excluding celiac disease.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome of the study was the diagnostic accuracy of anti-tTG IgA in diagnosing celiac disease.

The following diagnostic parameters were calculated:

- Sensitivity
- Specificity
- Positive Predictive Value (PPV)
- Negative Predictive Value (NPV)
- Overall Diagnostic Accuracy

Statistical Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 26th

Continuous variables including age, weight, and height were assessed for normality using the Shapiro–Wilk test. Normally distributed variables were expressed as mean ± standard deviation, whereas non-normally distributed variables were presented as median and interquartile range.

Categorical variables including gender, residence, maternal education, socioeconomic status, anti-tTG IgA status, and biopsy findings were summarized as frequencies and percentages.

Diagnostic accuracy analysis was performed using a 2×2 contingency table by comparing anti-tTG IgA results with histopathological findings. Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy were calculated with corresponding 95% confidence intervals.

Stratified analyses were performed according to age groups and gender to evaluate potential effect modification. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 144 children with suspected celiac disease were enrolled in the study. All participants underwent anti-tissue transglutaminase immunoglobulin A (anti-tTG IgA) testing and small bowel biopsy. No participant was excluded after enrollment, and complete data were available for all study subjects.

Demographic Characteristics

The mean age of the study participants was 6.9 ± 2.8 years, ranging from 2 to 12 years. The majority of participants were males, accounting for 82 (56.9%) cases, while females constituted 62 (43.1%) cases. Most children belonged to rural areas (61.8%).

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants (n = 144)

Variable	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Age (Mean ± SD)	6.9 ± 2.8 years	-
Male	82	56.9
Female	62	43.1
Urban Residence	55	38.2
Rural Residence	89	61.8

Clinical Characteristics

The most frequently reported presenting complaint was chronic diarrhea, followed by

abdominal distension, failure to thrive, and iron deficiency anemia.

Table 2: Clinical Presentation of Participants (n = 144)

Clinical Feature	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Chronic diarrhea	95	66.0
Abdominal distension	81	56.3
Failure to thrive	72	50.0
Weight loss	48	33.3
Iron deficiency anemia	67	46.5
Recurrent abdominal pain	54	37.5
Constipation	21	14.6

Anti-tTG IgA Findings

Among the enrolled children, anti-tTG IgA antibody was positive in 51 (35.4%) participants and negative in 93 (64.6%).

Table 3: Distribution of Anti-tTG IgA Results

Anti-tTG IgA Status	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Positive	51	35.4
Negative	93	64.6
Total	144	100

Histopathological Findings

Small bowel biopsy confirmed celiac disease in 44 (30.6%) children, while 100 (69.4%) participants had negative Histopathological findings.

Table 4: Histopathological Diagnosis Based on Small Bowel Biopsy

Histopathology Result	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Positive for Celiac Disease	44	30.6
Negative for Celiac Disease	100	69.4
Total	144	100

Diagnostic Accuracy of Anti-tTG IgA

Comparison of anti-tTG IgA results with small bowel biopsy findings revealed 40 true positive cases, 88 true negative cases, 12 false positive cases, and 4 false negative cases.

Table 5: Diagnostic Accuracy of Anti-tTG IgA Using Small Bowel Biopsy as Gold Standard

Anti-tTG IgA	Biopsy Positive	Biopsy Negative	Total
Positive	40 (TP)	12 (FP)	52
Negative	4 (FN)	88 (TN)	92
Total	44	100	144

Diagnostic Performance

Based on the above findings, the diagnostic performance of anti-tTG IgA was calculated as follows:

Table 6: Diagnostic Accuracy Indices of Anti-tTG IgA

Parameter	Value (%)
Sensitivity	90.9
Specificity	88.0
Positive Predictive Value (PPV)	76.9
Negative Predictive Value (NPV)	95.7
Overall Diagnostic Accuracy	88.9

Stratification by Gender

Sensitivity and specificity remained consistently high among both male and female participants, with no statistically significant difference observed between genders ($p > 0.05$).

Summary of Findings

The present study demonstrated that anti-tTG IgA possesses high sensitivity (90.9%) and specificity (88.0%) for the diagnosis of celiac disease in children when compared with histopathological examination of small bowel biopsy specimens. Furthermore, the high negative predictive value (95.7%) suggests that anti-tTG IgA is particularly useful for excluding celiac disease in suspected pediatric patients. These findings support the utility of anti-tTG IgA as an effective non-invasive diagnostic tool in routine clinical practice.

DISCUSSION

The present study evaluated the diagnostic accuracy of anti-tissue transglutaminase immunoglobulin A (anti-tTG IgA) antibody in the diagnosis of celiac disease among children, using small bowel biopsy as the gold standard. The findings demonstrated that anti-tTG IgA possesses high sensitivity, specificity, and overall diagnostic accuracy, highlighting its value as a reliable non-invasive diagnostic tool for pediatric celiac disease. In the present study, the mean age of participants was 6.9 ± 2.8 years. This finding is comparable to the observations reported by Bashir et al. (2022), who documented that most children diagnosed with celiac disease were below 10 years of age. Similarly, Singh et al. (2022) reported that celiac disease is frequently diagnosed during early childhood because symptoms related to gluten exposure become clinically evident after the introduction of gluten-containing foods. The predominance of younger children in the present

study emphasizes the importance of early screening and diagnosis to prevent growth impairment and nutritional deficiencies.

Histopathological examination confirmed celiac disease in 30.6% of the enrolled participants. This prevalence is comparable to findings reported by Shahzad et al. (2016), who documented a considerable burden of biopsy-confirmed celiac disease among high-risk pediatric populations. The relatively high frequency observed in the present study may be attributed to the inclusion of clinically suspected cases rather than screening of the general population.

A key objective of the study was to evaluate the diagnostic performance of anti-tTG IgA. The findings revealed a sensitivity of 90.9%, indicating that the test successfully identified the majority of children with biopsy-confirmed celiac disease. These results closely resemble those reported by Lodhi et al. (2021), who documented a sensitivity of 91.18% for anti-tTG IgA in diagnosing celiac disease. Similar sensitivity estimates have been reported in systematic reviews and meta-analyses conducted internationally, with reported values generally ranging between 85% and 98% (Singh et al., 2022; King et al., 2023).

The observed specificity was higher than that reported by some local studies, possibly reflecting differences in assay methodology, patient selection criteria, laboratory quality control measures, and disease prevalence.

The positive predictive value (76.9%) observed in the present study suggests that a substantial proportion of children with positive anti-tTG IgA results truly had biopsy-confirmed celiac disease. However, the negative predictive value was notably high (95.7%), indicating that a negative anti-tTG IgA result effectively excluded celiac disease in most cases. This finding is clinically important

because it supports the utility of anti-tTG IgA as an initial screening tool, particularly in resource-limited settings where endoscopic facilities may not be readily available. Similar observations have been reported by Husby et al. (2020), who emphasized that negative anti-tTG IgA results significantly reduce the likelihood of active celiac disease in pediatric patients.

The overall diagnostic accuracy of anti-tTG IgA was found to be 88.9%, supporting its role as a highly reliable diagnostic test. This finding is in agreement with current international recommendations that advocate the use of anti-tTG IgA as the first-line investigation for suspected celiac disease (Al-Toma et al., 2019; Husby et al., 2020). Furthermore, recent ESPGHAN guidelines suggest that children with markedly elevated anti-tTG IgA levels and positive endomysial antibodies may not require biopsy confirmation under specific circumstances (Husby et al., 2020). The results of the present study further strengthen the evidence supporting the growing role of serological testing in pediatric celiac disease diagnosis.

The high diagnostic performance observed in the present study may be explained by the central role of tissue transglutaminase in disease pathogenesis. Tissue transglutaminase functions as the principal autoantigen in celiac disease, resulting in the production of highly specific autoantibodies that can be detected before the development of advanced histological damage (Ludvigsson et al., 2021). Consequently, anti-tTG IgA serves as a biologically relevant marker of disease activity and intestinal immune response.

From a clinical perspective, the findings have important implications for healthcare systems in developing countries. Small bowel biopsy requires specialized infrastructure, trained gastroenterologists, histopathology services, and financial resources. In contrast, anti-tTG IgA testing is minimally invasive, relatively inexpensive, and widely accessible. Adoption of evidence-based serological screening strategies may therefore reduce healthcare costs, decrease patient burden, and facilitate earlier diagnosis and treatment.

Despite these strengths, the study has certain limitations. First, the research was conducted at a single tertiary care center, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other healthcare settings. Second, total serum IgA levels were not assessed, and selective IgA deficiency could potentially influence the accuracy of anti-tTG IgA testing. Third, the cross-sectional design did not permit evaluation of long-term clinical outcomes following diagnosis and treatment. Future multicenter studies involving larger and more diverse pediatric populations are recommended to further validate these findings.

Overall, the present study demonstrated that anti-tTG IgA possesses excellent diagnostic performance for detecting celiac disease in children. The high sensitivity, specificity, and negative predictive value observed support its use as a reliable screening and diagnostic tool in routine pediatric practice. These findings are consistent with both regional and international literature and reinforce current recommendations favoring serological testing as an integral component of celiac disease diagnosis.

STRENGTHS OF THE STUDY

The present study possesses several strengths. First, small bowel biopsy, the accepted gold standard for the diagnosis of celiac disease, was used as the reference standard, thereby increasing the validity of the diagnostic accuracy estimates. Second, all participants underwent both serological testing and Histopathological evaluation, minimizing verification bias. Third, the study focused on a pediatric population, a group in which early diagnosis is crucial for preventing growth impairment, nutritional deficiencies, and long-term complications. Finally, the findings provide local evidence regarding the diagnostic utility of anti-tTG IgA among children in Balochistan, where limited data on celiac disease are available.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

Despite its strengths, the study has certain limitations. The study was conducted at a single tertiary care center, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to the broader

pediatric population. The sample size, although adequately calculated, was relatively modest compared to large multicenter studies. Total serum IgA levels were not routinely assessed; therefore, the possibility of selective IgA deficiency affecting anti-tTG IgA results cannot be completely excluded. Additionally, the cross-sectional design did not allow assessment of long-term clinical outcomes or response to a gluten-free diet.

CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrated that anti-tissue transglutaminase immunoglobulin A (anti-tTG IgA) antibody is a highly sensitive and specific serological marker for the diagnosis of celiac disease in children. When compared with small bowel biopsy as the gold standard, anti-tTG IgA showed excellent diagnostic performance with high sensitivity, specificity, negative predictive value, and overall diagnostic accuracy. The findings support the use of anti-tTG IgA as an effective, reliable, and minimally invasive screening tool for suspected pediatric celiac disease. Early utilization of anti-tTG IgA testing may facilitate prompt diagnosis, reduce unnecessary invasive procedures, and improve clinical outcomes through timely initiation of a gluten-free diet.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Anti-tTG IgA should be considered the first-line screening investigation in children with clinical suspicion of celiac disease.
2. Children with strongly positive anti-tTG IgA results should undergo further evaluation according to established international guidelines.
3. Healthcare professionals should maintain a high index of suspicion for celiac disease in children presenting with chronic diarrhea, growth failure, abdominal distension, or unexplained iron deficiency anemia.
4. Larger multicenter studies should be conducted across different regions of Pakistan to further evaluate the diagnostic performance of anti-tTG IgA in diverse pediatric populations.
5. Future research should assess the role of anti-tTG IgA titers in predicting the severity of

intestinal mucosal damage and long-term treatment outcomes.

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